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NUMERICAL INVESTIGATION OF SENSITIVITY OF TORSION AXIS POSITION TO LOW PRESSURE TURBINE FLUTTER

Mizuho Aotsuka, Naoki Tani
IHI Corporation
Tokyo, Japan

Junichi Kazawa
Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency
Tokyo, Japan

ABSTRACT

Numerical study is conducted for LPT cascade flutter. 3 types of blades are examined by an annular cascade test rig. All blades have the same suction side profile, but have different pressure side profile. Blade 1 has a thin profile and blade 3 has a thick profile. Blade 2 has medium thickness between the blade 1 and 2. So the all blades have basically similar aerodynamic characteristics, but have different mechanical property. The experimental result show the blade 1 is flutter unstable, while other 2 blades are flutter stable. Flutter analysis by CFD show good agreement with the experimental results. It is clearly shown that the local aerodynamic damping coefficient of forward portion on the suction surface contributed to the flutter instability. This is caused by the change of the torsional axis. The unsteady pressure distribution does not depend on the torsion axis, but the blade movement is changed by the torsion result. Especially, a position of an intersection point between the base airfoil shape and the deformed shape contributes the blade stability.

INTRODUCTION

Since a modern jet engine must have very high performance with extremely low weight, cutting edge engines have very thin blade thickness. As a result, flutter becomes very important and severe problem, and sometimes it destroys whole engine due to blade fly-off^[1]. Therefore, proper evaluation of flutter onset is one of the most important and difficult problem.

There have been a lot of researches on its mechanism and evaluation technique. Among these activities, it became clear that torsion axis plays an important role to flutter onset^[3]. A contour plot of the location of torsion axis and its critical reduced velocity shows the flutter stability of the LPT blade. This contour plot is applicable for blade design.

Vogt et al.^[4] clearly shows torsion axis influence by forced vibration experiment, but its aspect ratio is

relatively small compared to actual LPT blade. This experimental result is one of the good validations of low aspect ratio blade, however, it is unclear that the same criteria can be applied high aspect ratio blade.

In 2014, Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency, JAXA, launched the advanced Fan Jet Research (aFJR) project^[2], which objective is to develop cutting edge technologies for low-pressure components of turbo-fan jet engine with high-performance and light weight at the same time. Among them, turbine flutter is one of the major research objectives.

Authors have conducted some flutter experiments to evaluate the flutter stability change due to the position of the torsion axis. In these experiments, our purpose is to evaluate the aerodynamic damping at flutter condition. So authors have developed a simplified experimental rig to evaluate the aerodynamic damping with minimizing the friction damping. The test rig has a full annular cascade, which is an integrated part composed of blades, hub platform ring and shroud ring. It is seamless design and the hub and shroud ring are very rigid, so the blade oscillation is supposed to be blade only mode shape and the friction damping is minimized.

As for the blade design, we designed 3 types of blade, each blade has the same suction side profile but has another torsion axis. So these blades have similar aerodynamic loading, but have different flutter stability. A flutter is observed for one type of blades, which has its torsion axis in a flutter unstable region in the 2D screening chart.^[10]

Authors developed a CFD code for flutter analysis based on the UPACS code, which is originally developed by JAXA. Flutter analysis is conducted for the 3 blades. The CFD results are compared with the experimental data. The predicted flutter stability shows good agreement with the experimental results. So we concluded that the CFD captures the flutter characteristics properly. And we conducted further investigation of detailed flow field.

NOMENCLATURE

IBPA : Inter Blade Phase Angle

C_p : Pressure coefficient = $\frac{ps - ps_{in}}{pt_{in} - ps_{in}}$

$\overline{C_p}$: Unsteady Pressure Coefficient

Chord: Chord length

IBPA: inter blade phase angle

Vr: reduced velocity = $\frac{U}{\omega \cdot 1/2 \text{ Chord}}$

M: Mach number

p: pressure

U : Blade exit velocity

W : Aerodynamic work per cycle

C : Blade / grid amplitude in complex form

A, B : Component of blade / grid amplitude C

X : Blade / grid displacement

\dot{X} : Blade / grid velocity

T : Period of blade oscillation

ω : Blade vibration angular velocity

Experimental Method

The flutter experiment is conducted at the JAXA Altitude Test Facility, JAXA ATF [5]. JAXA ATF test facility was originally designed to test whole engine or engine component at high altitude condition by suctioning chamber air from the downstream. This strong suction performance can be used to generate high flow rate by adopting enclosed test section at the air inlet.

In order to generate flutter, blade aspect ratio must be set high compared to an actual jet engine blade, and blade loading must also be enough high. While on the other hand, except for these two parameters, the other design parameters, such as exit Mach number, must be set to near a jet engine condition for comparison of jet engine design criteria. Blade aspect ratio is nearly 9 to reduce structural natural frequency. The ATF inlet is exposed to open air, therefore, inlet condition is equivalent to atmospheric condition.

The blade design completely followed the same methodology and criteria as the actual blade design for a jet engine, except for the flutter criteria. We tested 3 types of blade. Figure 1 shows the blade profile of each blade at mid span position. Blade 1 was designed thin enough to reduce natural frequency for flutter onset. Blade 3 has very thick profile to avoid flutter. And blade 2 has medium thickness between the blade 1 and 3. Basic aerodynamic design was set to the same between those three blades, so all blades have same suction surface profile, but they have different torsion axis. Figure 2 shows the Mach number distributions on the blade surface. The Mach number distributions for the blade 1 and 2 is almost identical, however the distributions for blade 3 is different from other two.

Figure 3 shows the mode shape (blade displacement calculated by FEM analysis) of the blades, and table 1 shows the reduced velocity based on the exit velocity at

50% span position. The blade 1 has the highest reduced velocity for both mode 1F and 1T.

Numerical Method

IHI and JAXA have collaborated on developing a CFD code for analysis of the turbomachinery. The code is based on the UPACS (Unified Platform for Aerospace Computational Simulation) [6] [7], which is originally developed by JAXA. The original version of the UPACS is multi-block Navier-Stokes solver for the external flow such as the flow around the airplane. At first, the UPACS was modified to be able to calculate the turbomachinery in the collaboration work. And then the new code was extended to analyze the blade oscillation flow [8].

The code is an unsteady 3D multi-block flow solver for the Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes equations using a cell-centered discretization. The moving frame of reference is introduced to the UPACS to be capable of turbomachinery simulation in terms of absolute variables.

Blade Oscillation Method

The blade oscillation is supposed to be harmonic in a specified mode shape. When each grid point which locates at the base position x_0 oscillates in the amplitude C, the phase lag θ , and the angular velocity ω , the coordinate of the grid X at the time t can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} X(x_0, t) &= x_0 + C(x_0)e^{-i(\omega t + \theta(x_0))} \\ &= x_0 + [A(x_0) + iB(x_0)]e^{-i\omega t} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where

$$C(x_0) = \sqrt{A(x_0)^2 + B(x_0)^2}, \theta(x_0) = \tan^{-1}\left(\frac{B(x_0)}{A(x_0)}\right)$$

The grid coordinate and velocity at the time t is written

$$\begin{aligned} x(x_0, t) &= \text{Re}(X) = x_0 + A(x_0)\cos(\omega t) + B(x_0)\sin(\omega t) \\ \dot{x}(x_0, t) &= \text{Re}(\dot{X}) = \omega(-A(x_0)\sin(\omega t) + B(x_0)\cos(\omega t)) = \omega \text{Im}(X) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

The components of the amplitude A and B are evaluated by the two grids, one is the grid at time t=0 and the other is at t=T/4. A and B are written as

$$A(x_0) = x(x_0, 0) - x_0, B(x_0) = x(x_0, T/4) - x_0 \quad (3)$$

For the blade oscillating calculation, three grids must be produced. One grid is base grid and two grids are deforming grids, one is the initial grid at t=0 and the other is the quarter grid at t=T/4. The deforming grids are produced based on the mode shape calculated by the FEM analysis. The numerical grid at each time step is produced by a kind of interpolation using these grids. Since the each grids have positive cell volume and good smoothness, the produced grid at each time step also has good quality, and therefore the blade oscillation calculation becomes robust.

Flutter characteristic analysis

The aerodynamic damping on the blade is calculated for the flutter characteristic analysis. When the aerodynamic damping becomes negative, the blade oscillation is unstable. On the other hand, if it is positive, the blade oscillation is stable.

The aerodynamic work per cycle can be written as

$$W = \int_{\text{BladeSurface}} \oint pe^{-i\omega t} \cdot \dot{X} dt \cdot (\vec{n} \cdot ds) \quad (4)$$

where $pe^{-i\omega t}$ is the pressure fluctuation, \vec{n} is normal vector. Replacing \dot{X} by equation (2), equation (4) becomes

$$W = \int_{BladeSurface} \oint pe^{-i\omega t} \cdot \omega(-A\sin(\omega t) + B\dot{\cos}(\omega t))dt(\vec{n} \cdot ds) \\ = \sum_{BladeSurface} -\pi \cdot B \cdot Im(p) \cdot (\vec{n} \cdot \Delta s) \quad (5)$$

where Δs is the area vector on the blade surface. And aerodynamic damping becomes

$$\zeta = -\frac{W}{2 \cdot K_E} \quad (6)$$

where $K_E = \frac{1}{2}M\omega^2$ is the maximum kinetic energy over one cycle of the blade motion. M is the modal mass and w is the modal frequency.

Numerical grid

The numerical grid is produced by a multi-block grid generation method developed by Yamamoto and Engel^[9]. The method is based on a flexible elliptic PDE (partial differential equation). The grid points on the blade surface are not constrained to some special points (i.e. leading edge and/or trailing edge). So it has more flexibility to distribution of the grid points, and it can produce better orthogonality around the blade surface and less skewness in the blade passages at the

Comparison of Experimental and Numerical Results

In the experiment, blade vibration is measured by strain gauges, and flutter onset point is determined by the amplitude and the inter blade phase angles with increasing mass flow from low flow rate to the design mass flow. The maximum strain vs mass flow rate is shown in figure 4. The blade vibration of the blade 1 shows drastic change at about 67% design mass flow. This change indicates onset of cascade flutter. And the mode of flutter is judged to be 1st torsion mode according to the oscillation frequency. The vibration of blade 2 and 3 does not show such drastic change, so there is no flutter for blade 2 and 3.

At the design mass flow condition, CFD analysis is conducted. Fig. 5 shows the aerodynamic damping ratio vs inter blade phase angle. The aerodynamic damping of the blade 1 has negative value from IBPA 240 to 360, while those of blade 2 and 3 are positive for whole inter blade phase angles. CFD results indicate the blade 1 is flutter unstable and the blade 2 and 3 are flutter stable.

Detailed Flutter Mechanism

Figure 6,7 and 8 show local aerodynamic damping distributions on the blade surface at IBPA 270 degrees, at which the aerodynamic damping of the blade 1 has the minimum value. Fig. 6, 7 and 8 are the results of blade 1, 2 and 3 respectively. Positive value contributes to stabilizing effect, and negative value contributes to destabilizing effect.

In the fig. 6, there is large negative value region on the suction surface from LE to mid-chord. As for the blade 2, in the fig. 7, there is similar negative region on the suction surface, but its size is much smaller than that of the blade 1. And there is positive region from mid-chord to TE. And for the blade 3, negative region is not recognized in the fig.8. The negative region on the suction surface is the main cause for the flutter instability of the blade 1.

Figure 9, 10 and 11 show the distribution of the local aerodynamic damping ratio at 50% span position. Fig. 9, 10 and 11 are results of blade 1, 2 and 3. In the figure, the horizontal axis is the chordwise position and the vertical axis is the local aerodynamic damping ratio. In order to see the relation with the deformation of the blade, the original blade shape and the deformed shape are over-plotted in the figure.

As seen in the figs. 6 and 7, for the blade 1 and 2, there is a region where the aerodynamic damping ratio becomes negative on the suction surface. For the blade 1, it reaches near the 70% chord position from the LE and for the blade row 2 it locates from the LE to the vicinity of the 50% chord position. On the other hand, the aerodynamic damping ratio takes a positive value in the backward area from the position where the aerodynamic damping is just 0.

For the blade 1, since the negative region is large and deep, the integral value in the entire blade becomes negative, and for the blade 2, the negative region and the positive region just cancel each other, and the total aerodynamic damping has a positive value.

Looking at the position where the aerodynamic damping switches from positive to negative, it can be seen that it is the point where the deformed blade intersects with the original blade. If the intersection point locates backward, there is large negative damping ratio area and small positive damping ratio area. Conversely if it is forward, the stable region gets wider. So the flutter stability depends on the inter section point.

The aerodynamic damping value on the blade surface is the product of the imaginary part of the unsteady pressure and the displacement of the blade according to the equation (5). The position of the intersection greatly affects the displacement of the blade, but at the same time it may possibly influence the distribution of the unsteady pressure.

Now, the value of the imaginary part of the unsteady pressure at 50% span is shown in figure 12, 13 and 14. For the blade 1 and 2, the signs of the imaginary part of the unsteady pressure on the suction side are both negative and their distribution shapes are similar. Therefore, if the blade load is similar, the unsteady pressure induced on the blade surface is almost the same, and it does not depend on the mode shape. Therefore, by changing the sign of the blade displacement vector by the mode shape, the sign of aerodynamic work is switched from negative to positive.

On the upstream side of the intersection of the blade surfaces, it contributes to the unstable and on the downstream side it contributes to the stable side. Therefore, flutter instability tends to occur when the intersection of the blade surfaces exists behind the blade.

Conclusion

Numerical study for three types of the LPT blade is conducted. The blades have the same suction side profile, but have the different thickness and modal property. The CFD flutter analysis results show good agreement with the experimental results. The following findings were obtained from the results of CFD analysis.

The local aerodynamic work of the upstream region on the suction side contributes to the instability of the blade cascade.

The unsteady pressure caused by the vibration of the blade is not influenced much by the position of the torsion axis.

The local aerodynamic work depends on the unsteady pressure of the blade surface and the displacement vector of the blade. The direction of the vector depends on the position of the torsion axis, and the aerodynamic work in the area upstream of the torsion axis contributes to instability, and it in the downstream area stabilizes the blade vibration. Therefore, the instability becomes stronger as the torsion axis is getting more behind.

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Fig. 1 Blade profiles

Fig. 2 Mach number distributions on blade surface

Fig. 3 Mode shape for mode 1F and 1T

Table 1 Reduced Velocity

	1 st Flex	1 st Torsion
Bld 1	4.30	2.85
Bld 2	3.68	2.16
Bld 3	3.53	0.92

Fig. 4 Maximum Strain vs Mass Flow (exp)

Fig. 5 Aero damp calculation results @ design mass flow (CFD)

Fig. 6 Local Aero damping coefficient distribution Blade 1 @ IBPA270 deg.

Fig. 7 Local Aero damping coefficient distribution Blade 2 @ IBPA270 deg.

Fig. 8 Local Aero damping coefficient distribution Blade 3 @ IBPA270 deg.

Fig. 9 Local Aero damping coefficient distribution @50% Span Blade 1 @ IBPA270 deg.

Fig. 12 Imaginary part of unsteady pressure @50% Span Blade 1 @ IBPA270 deg.

Fig. 10 Local Aero damping coefficient distribution @50% Span Blade 2 @ IBPA270 deg.

Fig. 13 Imaginary part of unsteady pressure @50% Span Blade 2 @ IBPA270 deg.

Fig. 11 Local Aero damping coefficient distribution @50% Span Blade 2 @ IBPA270 deg.

Fig. 14 Imaginary part of unsteady pressure @50% Span Blade 3 @ IBPA270 deg.